

THE IMPACT OF FARMERS AND HERDERS CONFLICTS ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES IN BOKKOS LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA COUNCIL OF PLATEAU STATE

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the impact of farmers and herdsmen conflict on socio-economic activities in Bokkos Local Government Area Council of Plateau State from 2010-2024. The year 2010-2024 witnessed conflicts between farmers and herdsmen in Bokkos Local Government Area council of Plateau State of Nigeria, that has resulted in the destruction of lives and property, massive internally displaced persons, closure of schools including Plateau State University Bokkos, reprisal attacks, closure of daily and periodic markets, food insecurity and psychological trauma on innocent citizens residing in Bokkos Local Government Area Council of Plateau State. The paper adopted the environmental scarcity theory which states that environmental changes, population growth asymmetric or unequal social distribution of resources, and the struggle/competition for these scarce resources lead to violent conflicts. The methodology adopted by the paper was descriptive survey research design which involved collection of data through primary and secondary methods. The Major findings revealed that herders-farmers conflicts are prevalent in Bokkos Local Government Area council and have resulted in the destruction of lives and property crops damaged by cattle, struggle for land space, cattle rustling, internally displaced persons, closure of schools both primary and tertiary institutions and disregard for rules and regulations. The study recommended that arrest and prosecution of offenders, improved training for the security and law enforcement agencies, the involvement of traditional rulers who have good integrity and are the custodians of culture in conflict resolution, enhanced public information and education on the need citizens to respect and obey the law and engage in dialogue to promote peaceful and harmonious co-existence.

Keywords: Conflict, Farmers, Herders, Socio-economics development.

INTRODUCTION

Bokkos local government area council of Plateau State, Nigeria consists of good farming lands and an arid zone, the prominent areas of Bokkos Local Government Area Council are Bokkos, Maikatako, Toffa, Kilba, Maiyanga, Mbar, Tanti, Toff, Mushere, Dafo, Batura, Bot, Folof, Kof, Ambul and Manguna which are good fertile lands for farming. They are only one of their kind in this local government in Bokkos local government. Their good fertile lands are productive natural systems that are of great economic importance and many of these communities in Bokkos local government area council are heavily dependent on these fertile lands to support livestock food and other cash crops that are required locally and nationwide.

These fertile lands in Bokkos local government area council of Plateau State have a lot of pressure as a result of their fertility and therefore could produce high value cash crops such as Irish Potatoes, rice, maize, vegetables, millet, groundnuts, Tamba, wheat, and Bambara nuts. However, the fertility of these lands has increasingly become a serious problem or source of conflict over the last fifteen years. A market survey in Bokkos local government area council was carried out on both daily and periodic markets to affirm the economic importance of fertile lands in Bokkos local government area council to the Bokkos local government people, to the Plateau State, Nigeria, and its neighboring countries.

Bokkos local government area council fed Nigeria with Irish potatoes, Tamba, Maize, and millet. This was taken cognizance of by the Federal Government of Nigeria when it introduced the National Fadama Development Project, especially in growing Irish potatoes, millet Tamba, and Maize. The introduction of irrigation farming popularly known as (Lambu) in the Hausa language by the use of water pumping machines increased the economic importance of the area which needed to be conflict-free of food products must be continued. Bokkos local government area council was well known for its Irish potatoes which were sold as far as Port-Harcourt, Lagos, Kano, Sokoto, Katsina, and Enugu among others. The production of these Irish potatoes, maize, Tamba, and millet was decreasing due to prevalence conflicts between farmers and herders in Bokkos Local Government Area council of Plateau State. The root causes of these conflicts were still to be studied in depth. The Plateau Agricultural Development Programme Staff and Agricultural Unit of Bokkos Local Government confirmed during the study survey that the quantity of Irish potatoes, maize, Tamba, and millet is declining as a result of farmers and herdsmen.

According to the programme manager of Plateau Agricultural Development Programme (PADP) Bokkos Local Government Area Council had the largest number of livestock in Plateau State. More than 80% of these livestock are owned by the Pastoralists (Bitrus 2024). In the opinion of (Shalangwa, 2024), the population of cattle for instance varied from about 200,000 in the wet season to over 500,000 in the dry season. The number of other livestock such as goats, and sheep probably exceeds close to a million. As a result of climate change, population explosion, expansion in buildings, food production as the mainstay of the people of Bokkos, and decreasing grazing land, pastoralist grazing areas became restricted and as a result decrease in the stocks and the consequence of the shortage or declining breeds conflicts and struggle for control of lands between the farmers and herders, in Bokkos. To buttress this view some of the pastoralists' who responded in Tanti, Maikatko, and Bokkos responded that they were looking for an alternative means of survival such as going into farming, doing cyclist work, and trading, that leads to indigene settler dichotomy that breeds conflicts which led to deaths and destruction as we experienced between 2001-2008 Jos north and its environs conflicts, The issue of farmers-herders conflict is not only peculiar to Bokkos Local Government Area Council but to other local governments in Plateau State such as Langtang North and South, Bassa, Ryom, Mangu, Barkin Ladi and other parts of Nigeria such Uzouwani in Enugu State where over fifty thousand people were killed, in Benue State in Guma, Agatu and Logo Local Governments was over two hundred people have lost their lives as a result of farmers-herders clashes. In as much as open grazing is allowed many conflicts are bound to occur in the future. This paper examined the impact of farmers'-herders' conflict on the socio-economic activities/development of Bokkos Local Government Area Council of Plateau State.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this paper is to examine the impact of farmers and herdsmen conflict on socio-economic activities in Bokkos local government council of Plateau state. Other specific objectives:

- I. Develop an assessment of the underlying causes of the conflict in the area
- II. Assess how the conflict has affected socio-economic development/activities in Bokkos local government area council of Plateau state.
- III. Assess the responses of government and non-governmental organizations towards mitigating these conflicts.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a mixed methodology which involved qualitative and quantitative research. The quantitative involved descriptive survey research design, and the study population was 1450. The **Taro Yamani formula of (1967)** statistics was used to draw ninety respondents through a questionnaire instrument that was used for data collection, and the qualitative involved secondary sources of data collected. Data were analyzed using simple percentage calculation based on the use of statistics while the secondary sources were analyzed using existing literature from research papers/ articles, published textbooks, Journals, Magazines, newspapers, Internet sources, online publications-journals, and Seminars.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY AREA

Physical Environment

Bokkos Local Government Area Council has its headquarters in Bokkos town. It houses the Plateau State University and is occupied by the Kulere, Ron, and Mushere peoples. Bokkos Local Government Area has an area of 1,6821cm² and had a population of 178,454 in the 2006 census. This Local Government Area occupies the western axis of Plateau state. It is bordered by Mangu, Qua'an Pan, and Barikin Ladi Local Government Areas. Bokkos Local Government has eight districts which are Bokkos, Mushere, Daffo, Sha, Manguna, Richa, Toff, and Kamwai. There are 20 electoral wards in Bokkos the Paramount ruler of Bokkos is called Saf Ron, he is the chairman of the Bokkos traditional council.

Bokkos is one of the most popular and major Local Governments among the seventeen (17) Local Government Areas of Plateau State. Bokkos local government is located in the northeastern part of the central zone of Plateau State. The creation of this local government was carved out of the then-Mangu local government area. This area was under the jurisdiction of the then Pankshin division which comprises the local government areas that are called the present-day central zone.

Bokkos local government area was created in 1980 during the Second Republic when Aihaji Shehu Shagari was the President of Nigeria under the NPN — (National Party of Nigeria).

Mr. Solomon Lar under the NPP (Nigerian's People Party) was the Governor of Plateau State including Nasarawa. At that period the senator was Garba Matta for the Central zone of which both of them are of blessed memory. Within this period the L.G.A. secretariat was built up in the center of the L.G.A. at Tudun Bokkos. It was built by the late Solomon Daushep Lar who was

the governor of Plateau. After the Second Republic which starts from 1979-1983. There was a coup by the military (Muhammadu Buhari, who became the military President of Nigeria with Navy Captain S. B. Atukum as the Governor of Plateau State]. Bokkos Local Government rematched again with Mangu Local Government Area. In 1985, the regime of Buhari also faced the challenge of coup d'état of Major General Babangida in 1985. This was another opportunity or grace for the recreation of Bokkos Local Government Area, which is still in existence to this present day with its headquarters at Bokkos.

In the area of studies, there are many dialects but the major one is, the Ron which is popularly known as "Chah" This ethnic group happens to be the one experiencing the present challenges of farmers and herdsmen clashes. The second major ethnic groups are the Kulere people, who are also believed to have come from the same place as the Ron people. That is to say, they have the same ancestral paternal lineage. These studies will center on the Northern part of Bokkos L.G.A where the farmers and herdsmen conflict are highly concentrated.

Typology of Producers

The economic activities in Bokkos local government area of Plateau state were of four main activities namely: farming, Agro-pastoralists, pastoralists, petty trading, and mining. The majority of the economic activities are in farming while the Agro-pastoralists came second. In recent times, many herdsmen have engaged in farming due to difficulty in acquiring land for grazing. Some of these herdsmen in Bokkos had turned into sedentary farmers who moved in and out of Bokkos for greener pastures. The traders also engage in buying and selling produce from the farmers while the miners engage in buying raw tin from the illegal miners,

Crop Production

Four main types of cropping systems are practiced in Bokkos namely; Fadama, raw fed, upland, and Lambu or irrigated. The Fadama farming system was introduced by the federal government to assist farmers through dry season farming by giving soft loans to farmers. The renowned is seasonal farming that takes place in every rainfall within the year. Upland farming is similar to raw fed where farmers cultivate in every rainfall within the year, irrigated is practiced either as a water pump near streams or ponds during the dry season, and it is popularly called Lambu farming in Abuja.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATIONS

Conflict

One of the most crucial definitions regards conflict as a struggle over values and claims to scarce status, power, and resources in which the opponents aim to neutralize, injure, or eliminate their rivals. (Coser 1956:8) in the same sense, conflict may be conceptualized as a way of settling problems originating from opposing interests and the continuity of society. Conflict is defined in many ways; there is no unanimity among scholars about what constitutes a conflict. One school, dominant in North America, defines conflict in terms of a clash of interests between two parties. Kenneth Building, for instance, states: "Conflicts over interests are situations in which some change makes at least one party better off and the other party worse off, each in their estimation. A fight is a situation in which each party to a Perceived conflict over interests acts to reduce the welfare of the other" Johan Galtung, who represents another school, maintains that "injustice and structural violence" mark a conflict situation. According to him, the absence of physical violence and confrontation between actors does not necessarily mean that structural violence is absent. Adam Curie (1990), presents a broader definition. For him, conflict is a situation where the "potential development" of one party is "impeded" by another. However, the most widely used definition links a conflict situation with the "incompatible goals" of parties. According to Michel Nicholson, (1988), "A conflict exists when two people wish to carry out mutually inconsistent acts. The definition of conflict can be extended from single people to groups and more than two parties can conflict. The principles remain the common element found in all definitions of regent goals and interests of two actors or parties who resort to various means in achieving their objectives.

Conflict is present when two or more parties perceive that their interests are Lille, express hostile attitudes, or pursue their interests through actions that the other parties. These parties may be individuals, small or large groups, and entries." Conflict is "a social factual situation in which at least two parties (individuals, states) are involved, and who: strive for goals which are incompatible to begin with or strive for the same goal, which, can only be reached by one party; and/or want to employ incompatible means to achieve a certain goal." (A. P. Schmid, Quoting Wasmuth in Thesaurus and Glossary of Early Warning and Conflict Prevention Terms (1998).

Pastoralism

According to Azarya (1996), pastoralism refers to an economy that is based on raising livestock which could be undertaken by sedentary or nomadic groups. Nomadism on the other hand depicts the extent of spatial movement of the groups in question. Thus, it is acknowledged in the literature that the question of pastoral production is conceptually different from the extent of residential mobility. Analyzing this line of argument further, some researchers like Salzman (1980) have affirmed that it is possible to have multi-resource nomadism. This entails mobile groups who may combine cultivation, hunting-gathering, sale of labor as well as livestock herding. On its part, pastoral involves the management of domesticated animals from which food is extracted and it can be carried out from a fixed location. While nomadism and pastoralism are not necessarily inclusive, it is also necessary to note that nomadism represents an integral lyrical and environmental dimension of pastoralism. It represents the technique of pastoralism since it is a movement among others; to avoid a wide range of the social and physical environment, an option not normally available to people who are tied to the agricultural lands and their stored agricultural products. Pastoralists may move with their herds to avoid insects and diseases to edition with other groups; and to avoid would be authorities (Dyon-Hudson -Hudson, 1980:17-18).

There are a few inventories of pastoral people in Nigeria which consist of the Fulbe, the Kanuri-related groups, the Shuwa, the Yedina, and the Uled Suleiman. However, the Fulbe (Fulani) are the most numerous and widespread and they have migrated eastwards the Gambia River over the last thousand years and probably entered Nigeria in the fourteenth century (Moritz, 2003:1). The Nigeria Fulbe are described by several classic authors, most notably de St. Croix (1994), Hopen (1959) and Stenning (1995) who study pastoral clans in semi-arid areas. For the humid and sub-humid regions, there is relatively little descriptive material. Awogbade (1983) describes the Fulbe on the Jos Plateau while some of the papers in Blench (1999) deal with pastoralists in southern Zaria.

On the other hand, the Koyan, Shuwa, and related peoples have remained in the semi-arid area of Lake Chad. They do not enter into contact with farmers except their atomic group, cultivating around river valleys or catching cropping at the foot of dunes. However, change in ecology and pressure on grazing has produced some surprises among the Uled Suleiman, camel herders of Libyan origin who now migrate between Niger and northeast Nigeria. The desiccation of several former wetland areas Coupled with pressure on grazing resources, made them explore further south and the High levels of water abstraction that are making the Hadeja-Nguru wetlands dry up

(Blench, 2003) have benefited the Uled Suleiman by making parts of the zone accessible to camels during the dry season. None of the other pastoral peoples in Nigeria has expanded in the same way as the Fulbe or Fulani. Therefore, conflict of the sort which is common among the Fulbe is not usually conceived as a problem.

Crop Farming (Sedentary Crop Farming)

Sedentary farmers are those farmers who live permanently in settlements, gaining their livelihoods mainly from crop production, with domestic animals providing supplementary income and practicing crop farming (Hussein, 1998). Thus, lowland dry farming systems are crop-livestock production, occupying about ten percent of the world's drylands and supporting ten times, the number of people that live under pastoral production systems. In such environments, unpredictable rainfall often creates acute shortages of food and unless livestock are few and integrated closely with crop production, overgrazing may occur and add to environmental degradation (UNRISD, 1997). It must however be noted that sedentary cultivators are also 'stock breeders' or 'herders'; and just as many stock breeders or herders are also to some extent, farmers. In essence, the links between 'farming' and 'herding' is a continuous rather than a separate one. Besides, while it may appear paradoxical, the emergence of pastoralism as a specialized economic activity was enhanced by the development of agriculture (Galaty and Johnson, 1990). Abba and Usman (2008) concur with this when they state that agriculture made it possible for the development of a regional system of complementary exchange between pastoralists and farmers.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Theoretical frameworks from the moment problems are discovered are developed for logical explanations of what is happening. The theory according to Shedrack (2004) helps analysts to situate their narration of the conflict within some existing theories of conflict. A theory is a set of related statements or hypotheses that have been tested and found to be valid against empirical evidence. Many scholars (Karl Marx, Homer Dixon, Weber, etc. and academia have propounded different conflict situations depending on the school of thought to they represent. As a result of this environmental theory was adopted in the work to better our understanding and knowledge of the conflict between farmers and herders in Bokkos Local Area Council of Plateau State.

Environmental Scarcity Theory

The environmental effects of human activity are a function of, first, the inerrability of the ecosystem and, second, the product of the total population and that population's physical activity per capita in the region. This theory was proposed, developed, and well-articulated best in the works of Homer-Dixon (1999) & Gizewski (1997). Homer-Dixon uses the term 'environmental scarcity' to refer to the scarcity of renewable resources. Homer-Dixon (1999) argues that environmental change, population growth, and unequal social distribution, are the three major sources of scarcity that lead to violent conflicts. First, Homer-Dixon identifies supply-induced scarcity, which is caused by the loss of resources such as a lack of quality drinking water or fertile land. Second, population growth and/or migration can increase the person's demand leading to demand-induced scarcity. Third, a skewed or disproportionate distribution of, or access to resources, is what Homer-Dixon terms 'structural scarcity'. These three types of scarcity are not mutually exclusive; they often occur simultaneously and interact. In this context, Homer-Dixon also considers the political economy of resource distribution, contending that the first two (sources of scarcity) are most pernicious when they interact with unequal resource distribution. However, these scarcities contribute to violence, only under certain circumstances. There is no inevitable or deterministic connection between these variables.

The nature of the ecosystem, the social relations within society, and the opportunities for organized violence, all affect causal linkages. The theory attempts to link conflict between multiple resource users to increase tension between these groups, emanating from growing vulnerability and insecurity of their livelihoods. It takes into cognizance, that conflict between multiple resource users is an unavoidable result of the competition for scarce natural resources, to achieve security of livelihood. Environmental scarcity produces four principal social effects: decreased agricultural potential, regional economic decline, population displacement, and the disruption of legitimized and authoritative institutions and social relations. These social effects, either singly or in combination, can produce or exacerbate conflict between groups. Most such conflicts are sub-national, diffuse, and persistent. For conflict to break out, the societal balance of power must provide the opportunity for grievances to be expressed as challenges to authority. When groups organized around clear social cleavages such as ethnicity, religion, religion, articulate grievances the probability of civil violence is higher. Under situations of environmental scarcity where group affiliation aids survival, intergroup competition based on relative gains is

likely to increase. As different ethnic and cultural groups are propelled together under circumstances of deprivation and stress, we should expect inter-group hostilities in which a group would emphasize its own identity while denigrating, discriminating against, and attacking outsiders (Homer-Dixon, 1999). He went on to show the complex interrelationship among environmental scarcity, social capital, population growth, migration, and the potential for violent conflict. In explaining why, a country may or may not resort to violence in the face of environmental scarcity, he emphasizes that urban unrest and/or rural insurgency occurs in the context of other variables. - Environmental scarcity is merely a contributing factor and is neither a necessary nor a sufficient cause of violent conflict. Other factors such as the adaptability of social structures (for example, market instability, the autonomy of the states, social norms, etc.) and a country's capacity or ingenuity in solving problems play a major role in whether a situation may become violent. Nevertheless, the environmental scarcity theory has received widespread scholarly attention, including those who have criticized it from the perspective of the political economy of scarcity. Dessler (2000) presents an overview of what methodology does to assist social science research and where Homer-Dixon's methodology falls short in his environmental scarcity theorizing. First, he outlines what two questions methodology seeks to answer in the case of environmental stress. The first question is predictive and asks if researchers can predict future levels of conflict from environmental trends. Second, the causal or explanatory question asks how environmental change brings about conflict. Two types of information could be used doxological questions.

The first is descriptive, in that, the information on the subjects under study are. The second type of information is broader; in general knowledge of what it is that the researcher is studying. This al discussion led to an examination of exogenous and endogenous boundary their impact on predictions of social/human behavior. The key problem. Dixon's work is that only one of the three scarcities discussed in his il scarcity theory is exogenous, and therefore, unaffected by other social.

Supply-induced scarcity is exogenous because it has nothing to do with humans but rather, with what resources nature has endowed the earth with. The remaining two demand-induced and structural are endogenous conditions that are affected by this theory is relevant and was adopted because the scarcity of the environment especially of cropland, freshwater, and

forests—contributes to violence in many of the world. These environmental scarcities usually do not cause wars among countries, but they can generate severe social stresses within countries, helping to late sub-national insurgencies, ethnic clashes, and urban unrest. Such civil violence particularly affects developing societies, because they are, in general, highly dependent on environmental resources and less able to buffer themselves from the social crises that environmental scarcities cause.

Environmental scarcity produces four principal social effects: decreased agricultural potential, regional economic decline, population displacement, and the disruption of legitimized and authoritative institutions and social relations. These social effects, either singly or in combination, can produce or exacerbate conflict between groups. In sum, the connection between environmental scarcity and conflict is indirect but important. Environmental scarcity is never the sole cause of conflict, but it is often an aggravating or contributing factor. Future efforts at conflict prevention and resolution should take the role that environmental scarcity plays into account which best explains this study.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

This section presents and analyses the data generated through the use of questionnaires and interviews. For this research, one hundred (100) questionnaires were distributed. Out of the one hundred questionnaires distributed only Ninety (90) were retrieved, seven (7) were missing and the remaining three (3) were invalid. Each questionnaire constituted Thirteen (13) questions directed toward verifying the assumptions of this research. The questionnaires were also divided into three segments; sections A, B, C, and D, the first section entails information about the bio-data of the respondent, the second section encompasses information about the causes of the conflict, the third section comprises the effects of the conflict on the community while the fourth section contains the responses by both governmental and nongovernmental organizations towards the conflict. The interview contains five (5) questions to complement the questionnaire.

Impact of the Conflict on the Plateau State Economy

The essence of this research shall be to measure the impact of the conflicts in Plateau State on the economy. This should be in quantifiable terms with particular reference to the areas of agricultural production, livestock production, commerce, shelter, and transportation in general terms some allusions have been made to the negative impact of the conflicts on the economy. For

instance, President Obasanjo in justifying the declaration of the State of Emergency in Plateau State stated, among other things, that:

"Violence has reached unprecedented levels and hundreds have been killed with many more wounded or displaced from their homes on account of their ethnic or religious identification. Schooling for children has been disrupted and interrupted; businesses have lost billions of Naira and property worth much more destroyed." (Obasanjo:2004).

President Obasanjo went further to observe that visitors and investors have fled or are fleeing Plateau State and the neighboring States have had their economies and social life disrupted and dislocated by the influx of internally displaced persons (Obasanjo:2004). To further stress this point the President said that the Federal Government and the neighboring States to Plateau State are incurring huge expenses in managing the socio-political and economic consequences of the near collapse of State authority and the breakdown of law and order in some parts of Plateau State and elsewhere. (Obasanjo:2004) Similarly in a Distinguished Annual Lecture presented to the National Institute, Kuru, in 2002 former President Ibrahim Babangida observed that the overall consequences of contemporary ethnic nationalism consist of the following among others:

"Wastage of enormous human and material resources in ethnically inspired violent encounters, clashes and even battles;" Threat to the security of life and property and disinvestments of local and foreign components with continuous capital flight and loss of confidence in the economy." "The heightening of fragility of the economy and political process." (Babangida:2002).

In a research report presented by Participants of the Senior Executive Course No. 26 of the National Institute, the economic consequences of religious and communal conflicts were noted as follows:

"In addition to the irreplaceable loss of lives, losses in terms of property (goods, houses, business premises) have not yet been fully ascertained. Some survivors have permanently lost. They labored for in their lives. As a result, one can safely argue that the aggregate of such instances negatively impacts the overall economy of these communities and by extension, the rest of the country. New armies of the unemployed, the destitute, and the highly aggrieved are added to the streets with their attendant consequences. Victims are also generally male and belong to the economically active segments of the society" (NIPSS: 2004).

The case for a negative impact of the conflicts on the economy would have been established, at least in principle with the general observations above. To domesticate this axiom to the economy of Plateau State it is necessary to document, measure, and quantify the extent of the negative impact of the conflicts on the economy within the period 2001 to 2004. Even from the above general observations a lot of research questions can arise. For instance, how many lives have been lost? How many houses have been destroyed? How many shops and markets have been destroyed? How many people have been displaced? How many investors have fled the State? How have the conflicts affected the level of production in agriculture, livestock, and industry? On the whole, what have been the cumulative effects of all these on the economy, particularly on the poor people in the State? It would be worthwhile to look more closely at the various sectors of economic activities in Plateau State to appreciate the negative impact of the conflicts in Plateau.

FINDINGS FROM THE QUESTIONNAIRE

Table 1: Q1. Sex of Respondents

Sex	No of Respondents	Percentage %
Male	66	73%
Female	24	27%
Total	90	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

The above table shows that 66 of the respondents representing 73% are Male, and 24 respondents representing 27% are Female. From the above it can be seen that Male are the majority of respondents with 73%.

Table 2: Q2. Distribution of respondents by age

Age	No of Respondents	%
18-20	8	9%
21-30	32	36%

31-45	30	33%
46 to above	20	22%
Total	90	100%

Source: *Field Survey, 2024.*

Table 9: Q3. How often does the farmer and herders conflict occur?

Response	No. of respondents	Percentage %
Constantly	67	74%
Rarely	23	26%
Total	90	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

The above table shows that 67 respondents representing 74% agreed that Conflict constantly occurs in the communities while 23 respondents representing 26% are of the view that conflict rarely occurs. From the above, it can be seen that the conflict occurs constantly with 74% as the majority of the respondents.

Table 10: Q4. What do you consider as the possible cause of the conflict?

Response	No. of respondents	Percentage %
Ethnicity	36	40%
Religion	30	34%
Land grabbing	12	13%
Cattle rustling	12	13%
Others	0	0%
Total	90	100%

Source: *Field Survey, 2024.*

The above table shows that 36 respondents representing 40% see ethnicity as the cause of the conflict, 30 respondents representing 34% see religion as the cause of the conflict, 12 respondents representing 13% know the struggle for land grabbing as the cause of the conflict, and also 12 respondents representing 13% see cattle rustling as the case of. We affirm that ethnicity is the underlying cause of the – herders’ conflict in Bpkkos LGA.

Table 12: Q6. How has the conflict-affected economic activities in the community?

Response	No. of respondents	Percentage %
Disruption of business activities	40	44%
Loss of produce in storage	20	22%
Inability to pay loans	10	11%
Scarcity of food items	20	22%
Total	90	100%

Source: *Field Survey, 2024.*

The above table shows that 40 respondents representing 44% say yes that the conflict disrupts business activities, 20 respondents representing 22% say that the conflict has caused loss of produce in storage, 10 respondents representing 11% say that it has caused those that collected loans not to be able to pay back, and 20 respondents representing 22% say that it has caused scarcity of food items. From the above the majority of respondents said that the conflict disrupts business activities in the communities are majority with 44%. We, therefore, affirm that business activities have been disrupted as a result of farmers-herders in Bokkos LGA of Plateau state.

Table 13: Q7. In what other ways has the conflict affected the communities?

Response	No. of respondents	Percentage %
Constraints in mobility	10	14%
Increased poverty	40	44%

Mutual distrust among the various parties to dispute	30	33%
Interruption in the education of children	10	11%
Total	90	100%

Source: *Field Survey, 2024*

The above table shows that 10 respondents representing 11% say that the conflict causes constraints to mobility, 40 respondents representing 44% say that the conflict has increased poverty, 30 respondents representing 33% say that the conflict has caused mutual distrust between the farmers and the herdsmen and another 10 respondents representing 11% says that the conflict causes interruption in children education From the above the respondents we assert that the conflict has increased poverty are the majority with 44%.

CONCLUSION

Without a doubt, Plateau State is very vulnerable to pastoralists and farmers' conflict as well as communal disputes. The majority of the respondents blamed the state government, for being largely responsible for the recurrent pastoralists and farmers in Plateau State that have led to the displacement of so many people from their original settlements and are now refugees in other places. Besides, the weakness and inability of the colonial methods and mechanisms of conflict prevention, management, and resolution which is the absence of conflict monitoring institutions was also responsible for the relatively high incidence of conflict between the pastoralists and farmers in the state. This has led to an increase in poverty (since they have no crops to sell as even the crops and farmlands were destroyed during the disturbances), insecurity, and underdevelopment of the state. This they maintained by saying that, how the government has handled past conflicts is not encouraging.

However, there are ways through which these conflicts are managed in these communities in particular and the state in general. They are indigenous (informal) and formal (contemporary/western) methods of conflict management. The populace preferred the indigenous (informal) method of managing conflicts to the formal (contemporary) method. As discussed in

this study, the informal approaches are Indigenous (African) methods used in resolving conflicts in the affected communities in particular and Plateau State in general, before the introduction and adaptation of the formal or contemporary approaches. These indigenous methods were very effective and reliable and conflicts were resolved with these methods immediately. These indigenous approaches were established in Plateau State and other communities in Africa with the sole aim of resolving relative peace in the communities. Above all, both parties prefer a collaborative method of managing this conflict to all other methods such as negotiation, arbitration, mediation, security agents, community meetings and adjudication, and a host of others that have been adopted in the past. This is because; they have not yielded any positive result, instead leading to the re-occurrence of the conflict.

From this study, it is a known fact that the human being is a sacred creature in the African context. Thus, killing of human being unjustly is an abomination. This is because our spiritual environment is occupied by the spirit which controls and sees the daily activities of the environment. This, if a person was killed unjustly in Africa, the gods of the land would be angry with such a person, and strange things would start happening in the community until the gods of the land were appeased. It is therefore advisable for the farmers and the pastoralists to adopt a collaborative method for managing the conflict rather than confrontational which always leads to violent conflicts. In essence, every group should shun violence to ensure peace and harmony. In sum, the government should collaborate with the different community leaders for an agreeable format and allocation of lands for pastoral purposes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Looking at the major findings of this research through the different methods applied, that is various answers from research questionnaires and interviews, the following recommendations are hereby made. This is in a bid to enhance the relationship between the farmers and pastoralists in Bokkos LGA and Plateau State as a whole, as well as improve the mechanisms for managing the conflicts if carefully studied and implemented.

I. Introduction of collaboration method of conflict resolution.

Collaboration assists in building trust, confidence and understanding among people. Thus, a direct collaborative method between pastoralists and farmers is recommended for the resolution

of the conflict. This is based on the fact that; those who collaborate and live together are more likely to establish intimate friendship and mutual respect among themselves than those who do not.

II. Revisiting the traditional system of conflict resolution

Before the advent of colonialism and the introduction of the western (that is, contemporary) methods of conflicts management, Africans had an efficient and rich cultural mechanism through which conflicts between groups, communities, states, kingdoms and even farmers and pastoralists were resolved. Such mechanism is part of the culture of the social formations in which it was practiced.

III. Social media

The government should make laws banning the spread of false rumors and spread of images and messages that are bound to Insite or increase tension and spread conflict through social media.

IV. Introduction of taxes

Also, payment of taxes on animals can be introduced. For example, as it was done in the Hausa *Sarauta* system the payment of *Jangali* was paid. These taxes can be used to provide security for the herders and their animals.

V. Revisiting past laws

Past laws should be revisited for example the laws that prohibits farming 70 metres to a main road and 50metres to a railway. These would allow enough space for the herders to pass without encroaching on the farms of the farmers.

VI. Politicians should be cautioned to desist from making statements that are inciting but rather make statements that will bring both parties of the conflict together to understand each other and not to antagonize each other.

VII. The role of the mass media.

Objective coverage and reportage should be the new norms for all media houses and reporters in Nigeria as well as other international media organizations. Reportage must be perceived to be a factual representation of events even in the face of protecting the sensitivity of events so as not to cause tension in society. The media must go beyond its cardinal roles and functions and imbibe the practice of conflict sensitivity, peace and conflict management, and journalism to make the public have a positive conception of media coverage and reportage. The issue of herdsmen and

farmers is one that if not carefully covered and reported with factual representation has the potential of becoming a conflagration that would eventually threaten the fragile state of coexistence and peace in Plateau State. Hence, media chiefs, workers, and organizations should guard against over sensational and sentimental reportage of the conflict.

VIII. Identification and punishment of erring culprits.

It was discovered during the research that most crises in the State, be it a conflict between farmers and pastoralists or land or any communal disputes, are sponsored by the elites. These personalities encourage and fan these crises by supplying arms and other destructive weapons to the youths as well as finance the crises. Therefore, the state government should identify and punish any personality involved in the promotion of any crises in the state. They should be stripped of their positions, and the government should prosecute them for criminal activities, capable of breaching public peace. These measures would serve as deterrence to other culprits and future troublemakers.

IX. The neutrality of the Nigerian armed forces.

According to some respondents, the police do not respond to distress calls and if they do, they are not prompt. In some cases, even after their arrival, they pitch a tent with one group (party) and arrest culprits of the other side. Many reasons were attributed to this. For example, they could be acting under instructions from influential politicians or personalities, who may be the owners of the farmyard or the owners of the animals in question. In this regard, the aggrieved party sees this act of the police as one of connivance and such a party is never ready to lay down its arms thereby prolonging the crises. Hence, the Nigerian police should always be fair, unbiased, and neutral in dealing with every conflict.

X. Provision of jobs/employment for the youths.

The provision of more jobs by the government at all levels would curb the high unemployment rate which is pushing the youths into promoting conflicts. If the youths were employed, they would not listen to unwholesome calls by selfish farmers and herdsmen to fight. In addition, social amenities such as electricity, good roads, water supply, and health facilities should be made available in rural communities to encourage the youths to set up small-scale businesses. This would discourage them from fighting since fighting would equally jeopardize their businesses and jobs as well.

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